

Effect of Self-Instruction on Attitude to Lying Among Secondary School Students in Anambra State

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Abstract

This study is on the effect of self-instruction on attitude to lying among secondary school students in Anambra state. One research question and one null hypothesis guided the study. Pre test, post test control quasi-experimental design was adopted. The population was 286 students who were identified by counsellors and class teachers to have positive attitude to lying in the 18 secondary schools in Awka South local Government Area in Anambra state. Two co-education secondary schools that had the highest number of liars were selected for the study. Purposive Sampling was used to select 64 students who scored above the norm of 75 in the instrument. Thirty-item researcher developed questionnaire, Lying Attitude Inventory structured on a five-point scale ranging from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree' was used for data collection. Mean and ANCOVA were used to answer the research question and test the hypothesis. Finding showed that self-instruction significantly reduced positive attitude to lying among students. Therefore, it was recommended that counsellors, teachers and significant others in secondary schools should adopt self-instruction technique in controlling attitude to lying among students.

Key words: *Self-instruction, Attitude to lying, Secondary school, Students*

Introduction

Most often, children lie in circumstances and events, even when it is more convenient, necessary and important to tell the truth. This may have resulted from the fact that lying is seemingly, generally acceptable by individuals, and has become a norm in the society.

Lying is the making of false statement with the intent to deceive. It is an intentional attempt to deceive or express what is false, or convey a false impression. Carson (2010) is of the view that lying requires making a statement that one warrants to be true. Thus, lying allows the speaker to manipulate the representation of truth according to certain social goals

Some adults in the homes and the society at large lie about things events and situations as such, they model lies for children. In the home for instance, a visitor comes to see a parent, he is told that the parent is not at home. The parent has instructed the children to tell the visitor so, whereas the parent is in the house but does not want to see the visitor. In the society also, people

lie about many things, in several occasions and circumstances. There is lying in education, business, the press and many other areas. Sadhguru (2016) collaborated by stating that people lie about where they are going. They lie to their family, spouse, boss, and whoever that is around them, on daily basis.

Lying originated from the devil who is known as the 'father of lies'(John 8:44). Lie is evil as it originated from the devil. It is among the vices instituted and practiced by many people in the society as normal. Hence, children imbibe this norm and live by it. This has lead to disorientation of many individuals' mind. To support this, Sadhguru (2014) remarked 'lying pull down life, prevent prosperity and leaves the mind completely disoriented'. Thereby, children leave their lives as automatic and authentic liars that lie about almost everything.

The causes of undesirable and maladaptive behaviour, which lying is, among students could be health problems, adjustment or developmental issues such as immaturity or self-esteem issues or general academic difficulties. In line with this, Abodike (2010) noted that undesirable and maladaptive behaviours in our society are deeply rooted in educational, political, social, economic, religious, health and psychological factors. In the school, teachers send children on private errands during school hours and lie about their whereabouts. Onlookers witness and practice same. These cause them to grow in the direction of negativity.

Self-instruction is an intervention that requires teaching a student how to use a positive statement to direct his or her own behaviour (Rafferty, 2010). It focuses upon giving the consumer the responsibility for instruction rather than relying upon a teacher or facilitator. Additionally, self-instruction is a cognitive-behavioural approach to self-control in which children are taught to use covert speech to modify their own behaviour. Children can be taught and they could learn and use a positive statement to control their own behaviour. This positive statement can be used to change positive attitude to lying to negative attitude.

The self-instruction procedure for this study was patterned after the work of Kamphaus, Reynolds and Vannest (2008) as follows:

- i. Model and verbalise necessary steps to complete the task.
- ii. Ask the students to complete the task while the therapist verbalizes the steps.
- iii. Ask the students to verbalize the steps and complete the task.
- iv. Ask the students to whisper the steps and complete the task.
- v. Ask the students to use the steps as silent talk and complete the task.

Lying among secondary school students has been noted by researchers such as Nwosu (2012) and Chinweuba (2010). These researchers observed the incidence of lying among secondary school students who lie and falsify real situations, without encouragement and motivation.

Some students have developed positive attitude towards lying as a result of their learning from the environment, the thought and belief that lying is acceptable, and a clever way to escape punishment and achieve desires. In trying to reverse this attitude, the therapist demonstrates that the positive attitude to lying resulted from the internalized wrong thought and belief. Therefore, she will inculcate the positive statement in the students, 'I must avoid lying in order to live positively, function well, and grow into a wholesome person'. These students will use this positive statement in the face of any situation that triggers them to lie.

Attitude is an expression of favour or disfavour towards a person, a place, a thing or an event. It is the relatively stable overt behaviour of a person which affects his status. Basically, attitude has two dimensions, and these are; positive attitude and negative attitude. Positive attitude to lying is being optimistic about lying, and denying reality. On the other hand, negative attitude to lying is to judge lying wrong (Hurka, 2014), and thereby accepting reality.

It is worth noting that previous studies on lying focused on the behaviour, and also, that the benefits associated with self-instruction is suggestive of its credibility in the control of attitude to lying. Having observed children, some of them with positive attitude to lying, the researcher desired to inculcate into children, the positive statement that can reverse their attitude to lying

Attempts by school teachers, parents and guardians to stop lying among children using admonitions and punitive measures, have proved abortive because they have been found to be ineffective. Also, most parents and concerned individuals in the society desire to have honest children and individuals who will grow and develop into wholesome persons. This study therefore, focused on how to reverse positive attitude towards lying among students to negative attitude. So put in question form, the problem of this study is how self-instruction will affect students' attitude to lying in Anambra state with the following research question and null hypothesis:

-What is the effect of self-instruction technique on attitude to lying of secondary school students when compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their pretest and post test scores?

-The effect of self-instruction technique on secondary school students' attitude to lying in Anambra state will not be significant when compared with those who received conventional counselling using their mean scores.

Method

The study adopted pre test post test control quasi experimental design. The population was 286 students. Purposive sampling was used to select 64 students from two coeducational schools that had the highest number of students with positive attitude to lying. There were 32 students in the experimental group and also 32 students in the control group. The instrument used for data collection was Lying Attitude Inventory (LAI), developed by the researcher. The instrument has 2 parts, A and B. Part A solicited information on the bio-data of the students while part B contained 30 items that has fifteen positive and fifteen negative statements. The participants were required to indicate their level of agreement with each statement choosing from a four-point scale of Strongly Agree, (SA, 4 points), Agree, (A, 3 points), Disagree, (D, 2 points), and Strongly Disagree, (SD, 1 point).

For the first fifteen items, the highest score was sixty (positive attitude) while the lowest was fifteen (negative attitude), and for the last fifteen items the highest score was sixty (negative attitude) while the lowest was fifteen (positive attitude). To get the total score for each participant, the values in the direct score items and those in the reversed score items were added up.

The face and content validity of the instrument were established by three experts, two in the Department of Guidance and Counselling and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all from

Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. A trial test was done using 20 participants. The scores obtained were used to establish the reliability measure of the instrument. Split half was done, and using Cronbach Alpha statistics, a reliability coefficient of $r=0.92$ was obtained. This was considered adequate for the study.

The specific self-instruction procedure used involved the following steps:

- i) Model and verbalise necessary steps to complete the task. Here, the therapist verbalised the self talk, 'I must avoid lying in order to live positively, function well, and grow into a wholesome person'.
- ii) Ask the students to complete the task while the therapist verbalizes the steps. Here, the students gradually developed the urge to eliminate favour towards lying, as they attentively focused on the therapist, while she strongly, strictly and emphatically verbalized the positive statement.
- iii) Ask the students to verbalize the steps and complete the task. Here, the students were asked to verbalize the positive statement with full attention, concentration and focus in order to memorize and assimilate the statement.
- iv) Ask the students to whisper the steps and complete the task. In this step, the students were asked to whisper the positive statement with attention, concentration and focus.
- v) Ask the students to use the steps as silent talk and complete the task. Here, the students were asked to internally say the positive statement to themselves, in the face of any situation that triggers them to lie.

The control group was given conventional counselling on the origin, causes and consequences of lying.

Data collected were analysed using mean scores to answer the research question and ANCOVA to test the hypothesis

Results

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest Attitude to Lying Mean Scores of Students Treated with Self-instruction Technique and those Treated with Conventional Counselling (Norm = 75.00)

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Self-instruction	32	77.25	22.19	55.05	Effective
Control	32	76.94	61.93	15.01	

Table 1 revealed that the students treated with self-instruction technique had pretest mean score of 77.25 and posttest mean score of 22.19 with lost mean 55.05 in their attitude to lying, while those in the control group who received conventional counselling had pretest mean score of 76.94 and posttest mean score of 61.93 with lost mean 15.06. The two groups post test mean scores reduced below the baseline which is 75. However, in comparison, the mean loss for self-instruction is far greater than the mean loss for conventional counselling. Therefore, self-instruction technique is considered effective in reducing the students' attitude to lying in Anambra state.

Table 2: ANCOVA on the Attitude to Lying Posttest Mean Scores of Students Treated with Self-instruction Technique and those who received Conventional Counselling

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	25408.245	2	12704.123			
Intercept	0.276	1	0.276			
PRETEST	127.245	1	127.245			
METHOD	25390.296	1	25390.296	754.23	0.00	S
Error	2053.505	61	33.664			
Total	140694.000	64				
Corrected Total	27461.750	63				

In table 2, it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 61df denominator, the calculated F is 754.23 with Pvalue of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effect of self-instruction technique on secondary school students' attitude to lying is significant.

Discussion

In the analysis of data collected in respect to the research question, it was discovered that self-instruction was effective in reducing attitude to lying among secondary school students in Anambra state in contrast with the hypothesis. This is because students treated with self-instruction have their attitude to lying significantly reduced below the norm of 75, when their mean loss is compared with that of the control group.

This finding is in line with. Adani, Eskay and Onu (2012) who observed that self-instruction is a self strategy that contributes to an individual's self determination skills, and it is an easy procedure to develop, learn and use. Additionally, Azza and Eman (2017) pointed out that through self-instruction, learners become active, and learning shifts focus from the teacher and delivery of course content to the students and active engagement with the material. The effectiveness of self-instruction on the students' attitude to lying has proved that the treatment package is reliable and self-instruction useful in solving human problem.

Conclusion

This study revealed that self-instruction is an effective counselling technique for reversing positive attitude to lying among students in secondary schools. Therefore, self-instruction should be adopted in schools to reduce attitude to lying among students.

Recommendation

Secondary school guidance counsellors, teachers and significant others should adopt self-instruction technique as a means of controlling attitude to lying among their students. The technique should be taught to stakeholders in education process, so that they learn and use it to manage the behavioural challenge among students.

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